

ISic0959

I.Sicily inscription 0959

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8723

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κίτε Κωσστ
2. αντία ἐτῶν εἴκοσι
3. μηνὶ Φρεβρουαρίῳ τ
4. ἕξ εἴκοσι τεσάρους ἡμέ
5. ρα Ἡλίου· ἥδιος τόπος
6. ἀγορασθέντος ὀλοκοτ
7. ἴνου
- 7a. □

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492589
EDCS 39102116
PHI 140440
PHI 175712

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0142 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 112

Carini, I. 1875. Rassegna archeologica. *Archivio Storico Siciliano*. 3: 121-125. At 124 no.30

Strazzulla, V. 1897. Museum epigraphicum: seu inscriptionum Christianarum quae in Syracusanis catacumbis repertae sunt corpusculum. *Documenti per servire alla storia di Sicilia : 3. ser.* Palermo. At no.82

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